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THE DEVELOPMENT OF NETWORK AND MEDIA CULTURE IN YOUTH LIBRARY FACILITIES

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This study is focused on the activities of Ukrainian libraries for youth, as well their role in the development of informational and network media culture and media awareness amongst youth. Through monitoring of the reporting of youth libraries and content analysis of websites, blogs and social networking pages the existing library facilities in the creation of youth information networks and media culture were uncovered. Method of comparative analysis has allowed to compare the selected library facilities for the creation of youth informational networks and media culture with focus on the individual psychological characteristics of young people (during early and late adolescence) and specific features of the Ukrainian media education model. The existing methods and tools for the creation of information networks, and to enhance youth media competencies, relative to psychological and age-based factors were lighted. The possibility of adding libraries to the Ukrainian model of media education is also considered. Proved that one of the priorities, which require libraries to consolidate efforts, is a development of clear strategic actions in the network of youth libraries and the creation of networked information and media culture and to ensure this activity isn't chaotic, but purposeful and well organized.

Key words: media culture, youth, libraries, information network, media competencies, media education.

INTRODUCTION

Teenagers and youth are the most highly active category of Internet users (Internet Asotsiatsiia Ukrainy, 2018), and of various mobile technologies, in terms of quantitative figures. According to the results of sociological research conducted by libraries, the majority of youth spend 2-3 hours a day for online communication, the minority, for 4-5 hours (Krasii, 2014, p. 59). Most young people in Ukraine (80.2 %) believe that they could not live without a mobile phone and 72.3 % of young users declare that they cannot imagine their life without Internet services (Gorshenin Institute, 2013).

Even 4-5 years ago, young people used the Internet primarily to search for information and for communication. The results of sociological research in 2014 showed that the situation has changed somewhat, and that the level of network users has increased and that the majority of users today use networks for varied purposes, for training and work, watching movies, for reading books, in order to follow developments in the country and around the world, for communication, gaming, shopping, etc... (LB.ua, 2013; Krasii, 2014, p. 60). And we can safely state, with certainty, and more particularly in recent times, that communication technologies have become firmly entrenched in the daily activities of young people, they affect their minds and values, socialization and self-realization, and their ideas about themselves and others. In this context, the problem of developing youth media competency is very important, not only in terms of sufficiency in numbers of competent users, but also due to the high level of information network use, especially when taking into account the current realities of Ukrainians' information society and the presence of information aggression. The

first issue when countering various threats in the virtual information environment is knowledge, as well as skills which enable the effective use of on-line communication tools and minimization of the risks that are possible within network communication.

REVIEW

The issues of the formation of media culture among young people became acute with the wide introduction of Internet technologies into the social practice. Different aspects of library activity in the context of active using by young people the services of the Internet environment and the education of a generation of digital culture were studied by such scholars as B. Kinney (2010), L. Tripp (2011), I. McShane (2011), T. Yakushko and T. Yaroshenko O. (2012), S. Poyntz and P. Jennesia (2018).

Researchers emphasize the double role of the library: providing young people with opportunities for learning and practice new media literacy skills and with contexts for learning with digital media; describe an innovative library program (YouMedia) as a research-informed model for what is possible (Tripp, 2011); analyzes various aspects of using by library the interactive tools of Web 2.0 (McShane, 2011; Yakushko, Yaroshenko, 2012) and library efforts to bridge the digital divide (Kinney, 2010); examine how relations among youth, media culture, and learning have been understood since the turn of the last century (Poyntz, Jennesia, 2018).

The aim of this study, which is based on monitoring the library and information activities of Ukrainian libraries, which serve youth, is considering of the level of Ukrainian libraries activities in forming informational and network media competencies in the youth environment, identify the strengths and weaknesses of these activities and making suggestions of ways of improving their effectiveness.

METHOD

The study took place in two stages:

Stage I – monitoring the reporting of the documentation of youth libraries and content analysis of websites, blogs and social networking pages for the purpose of isolating and synthesizing existing library facilities in the creation of youth information networks and media culture.

Stage II – comparative, during which time the selected library facilities were compared for the creation of youth informational networks and media culture with focus on the individual psychological characteristics of young people (during early and late adolescence) and specific features of the Ukrainian media education model.

PARTICIPANTS

The study was focused on the activities of the State Library of Ukraine for Youth (SLU for Youth) and Regional Libraries for Youth (RYL).

RESULTS

The necessity for the creation the relevant level of information network and media competencies is rather acute in early adolescence, as it is before a person faces the challenges of professional, or workplace identity. At this time youth should understand their own interests, inclinations, abilities, and begin to develop their own life plans and try to take the first steps towards them. As computer technology and online communication services are an integral part of everyday youth life, they can be utilized to overcome difficulties and challenges. Internet communication – is the ability to communicate with peers, experts, and to undergo professional online testing, monitor the lab

our market, for familiarization with success stories of others etc... In addition, it is an opportunity to improve daily learning activities, for instance, it can deepen study in a favorite subject, there are training courses, lectures, you can listen to teachers' lessons, and learn from recognized experts from the best universities in the world, and so on.

In late adolescence, when there is a transition from youth to adulthood, new ways of self-realization and self-actualization are formed, requiring the acquisition of higher-level information and networking and media competencies. This ensures that online communication becomes more focused and creative, as users at this age increasingly attempt to present themselves, as well as their thoughts and achievements, through blogs, on social networking sites, and with photo and video sharing. These activities require critical-thinking, a willingness to make decisions, the ability to analyze, evaluation of networked information, to quote others, as well as to create resources. Lack of these competencies can lead to chaotic usage of online services and low efficiency in networked communication. Such difficulties can cause stress and frustration, situations that are likely for young users due to their increased emotional and hormonal states, which accompany the transition to adulthood (Bozhok, 2013, p. 188). Therefore, we can state that the level of informational and network media competencies, which the individual has during the late adolescence period, to some extent depends on the creation of «frustration tolerance» – the formation of a psychological resilience in young people that is based on self-confidence, the ability to accept life's challenges, and to learn from them, showing flexibility in their approaches to solving problems and to overcome difficult situations (Bozhok, 2014, p. 188). The high level of competence required for successful performance, in terms of information presentation in an information-based society, makes youthful users more confident in their knowledge, increases opportunities and will increase their «immunity» to negative situations, and increase productivity in a youth person's daily activities, thus, self-confidence will increase and sensitivity to stress and frustration will decrease.

The formation of informational and network media-culture requires an integrated approach, and therefore requires the attention of such institutions as the family unit, school, and after-school facilities: informational, educational, and cultural institutions. Usually, the first experience and familiarization with media a child receives is within the family unit, and then a basic knowledge of computer science, the fundamentals of the Internet, network security and ethics is acquired from education facilities. Ukrainian libraries participate in developing such skills as critical thinking, effective communication networking, creative use of online media, skills to analyse, evaluation of information and network media tests of different forms and genres, to quote and to create their own resources, and to instill motivation to improve informational and network media-culture throughout life.

Since 2009, the issue of the creation of youth informational and network culture has been developed by experts from the libraries for youth (teenagers). In this context, it has been studied and summarised in conjunction with international experience, techniques related to interactive sessions have been adapted, thematic online resources are being developed, collaborations between teachers and potential coaches are being established, reference and training materials for librarians and information materials for youth (monuments, bookmarks, comics, cards, magnets, etc.) are being published and distributed.

Over time, the activity of libraries in the creation of network of informational culture is complex, and today it is based on the following components:

- measures for the creation of informational and network culture of librarians;

- establishment and maintenance of library virtual offices, or favourites in the youth environment web platforms, (blogs, podcasts, social networking pages, online video collections, etc.), to create high-quality and secure information platforms for youth;
- measures aimed at creating a network of information and culture among youth and young adults.

Interactive education, which is a kind of active study that is considered quality learning, as its effectiveness is noted by experts from educational institutions, will be implemented, as soon as possible, so librarians need to be trained in order to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. Such training, since 2010, has been an effective form of dissemination of knowledge, skills acquisition and skill-set creation for youth specialists at the State Library of Ukraine for Youth was used to create a network and an information culture for youth and librarians. In that year, the library, through victory in the competition «Educational Innovative Library» (program «Bibliomist») and the project «Safe and Friendly Web Space» created the Training Center «Netiquette».

All interested librarians were invited to participate in training to develop skills for using information and communication technologies:

- To develop library internal documentation (provisions about site, virtual reference, online-services, instructions for personnel attached to on-line communication);
- Drawing up rules for using the Internet, electronic resources, online communication services;
- Proper citation of electronic resources;
- Safe, ethical behavior during correspondence, video communication, and the execution of electronic purchases;
- Developing strategies for supporting libraries' virtual presence in social media;
- Dissemination of knowledge, skills, abilities, forming the basis of information and network culture taking into account age-specific issues relating to youth;
- Distribution of acquired competencies in the library environment and the ability to motivate colleagues in the further acquisition of new skills and knowledge.

The training course was developed for youth, based on training and consisted of 6 logically related components of meaningful topics, such as: «Meet the net ethics: concept of net ethics, main category and location, abuse of net ethics», «E-mail of net ethics», «Netiquette 2.0» (in particular, the behaviour in blogs, electronic classrooms, reputation in social networks, etc.) «Citing of Electronic Resources», «Internet Security», «Mobile Etiquette».

Information and network culture is not limited to the knowledge and skills of netiquette, of course it should be considered along with technical and social skills. However, research at the State Library of Ukraine for Youth in 2009 «Web Communication, Netiquette: Attitudes of Librarians and Readers» showed rather low competence levels in issues of security and ethics, although there were satisfactory levels of technical competence. Security of young users is a determining factor in effective communication, that's why in the first version of the study program deals with issues related to information values, various risks and ways to counter them in a reasonable fashion are addressed primarily.

On the Internet, to help in the creation of informational network culture for users of the State Library of Ukraine for Youth, a comprehensive information service is supported and consists of the following resources:

- Site «Netiquette»;

- Blog «Web communication, Netiquette»;
- Representation in Facebook «Safe and friendly web space»;
- Video channel «Tips for Netiquette»;
- Info «Safe Netyketka»;
- Safe Netyketka page in social networks.

On the web site of «Netiquette» the access to a library user-created knowledge base was created. You can find the key «commandments» of ethical network advice to net users—beginners and more advanced users on video communication, mobile communication, email etiquette, game etiquette and the fundamentals of safe passage in different areas of virtual space. Also, the site presents freely available library authors' developments of information materials (bookmarks, postcards, comics about the adventures of Max and Christine, characters who were created by librarians, teenagers who are studying netiquette) and the methodology materials that all visitors can use to create netiquette and distribute it with events within their classrooms.

Blog «Web communication, Netiquette» contains posts, designed for young people, as well as for the parents and professionals who work with them. This is a space for communication with users on the topic of network culture and a place for the exchange of ideas, for those involved as library youth network experts, as well as potential experts, and volunteers who could support libraries' initiatives.

For early adolescents it is common to have an interest in becoming more adult, and the desire to communicate with adults increases. Youth discuss their life plans with teachers, close friends, and with those who they admire and whose opinions are important to them. However, although youth maintain relations with adults they maintain a certain distance, and sometimes passionately defend their right to independently solve problems that concern them personally (Podoliak, 2013). These issues prompted experts at the State Library of Ukraine for Youth to create a virtual library volunteer – Info consultant Safe Netyketka. The backstory of this virtual volunteer is that she is 16 years old and interested in network ethics – «Netiquette», and wants to share her knowledge with her peers. Info – is a virtual robot controlled by artificial intelligence that is the face of the netiquette project on the web site, social media and mobile applications. Librarians teach their virtual assistant to answer questions which often arise from users in the context of network culture. Netyketka knows all the «commandments» of netiquette and gives information about library education and offers useful online resources.

Project results:

- The accumulated knowledge base on cultural networking, developed by comprehensive online information resources, which are freely available to anyone interested in raising their knowledge levels related to informational and network media culture;
- The experience that was gained during the project was included in the textbook «Technology Web 2.0 for Development of Libraries and Users: New Possibilities of the Library Environment Development» [Yakushko, Yaroshenko, 2012], which provides training for librarians-trainers of regional training centers who acquire knowledge to then distribute in the professional environment of their regions;
- In co-operation with young readers, through which librarians gain new ideas and due to initiatives such as video advice clips like «Tips for beginner net users» that have been recorded and are available on YouTube.

With the development of Internet media, through which different users can actively get involved in content creation, the issue of informational network culture creation may be considered closer to media culture.

In order to form a media culture in Ukraine in recent years media education has begun to develop systematically, with the adoption in 2010 by the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences the «The Concept of Introducing Media Education in Ukraine» (Instytut sotsialnoi ta politychnoi psykholohii NAPN Ukrainy, 2010). In 2011 the Ukrainian experiment to determine the best model of mass media education in accordance with the terms of Ukrainian society was launched.

Today the domestic socio-psychological model of media education, which aims to form media literacy and competence, integrates the latest achievements of foreign media education, critical analysis of that education, and adaptations to the Ukrainian environment. This model involves a combination of protective and aesthetic, critical and creative models of media education. The basis of the Ukrainian model is a social-psychological approach, in which media culture is conceived as a product, and at the same time, a condition whereby there is interaction within the information space between subjects (Naidonova, 2012). Besides the fact that media education is understood as a part of general education of schoolchildren and students, scientists distinguish media education in cultural and recreational centers, remote media education, and independent (continuous) media education throughout life.

The study of activity of Regional Libraries for Youth (Teenagers) as informational, and cultural and recreational centers gives grounds to say that some of them purposefully, in cooperation with educational institutions and media representatives, organize media and educational activities, others – occasionally carry out certain activities, contributing to the formation of separate elements of media competence. As we see, the traditional mission of the library – is to spread literacy, knowledge and culture – does not lose its importance, but in terms of global social changes, takes on new aspects. Also, it should be stressed, that the study results show the ability of Ukrainian libraries to perform their main objectives in supporting the above-mentioned models of media education – protective, aesthetic, critical and creative.

The creation of youth media awareness and media immunity¹(Instytut sotsialnoi ta politychnoi psykholohii NAPN Ukrainy, 2010) using gradual integration, is foreseen through the protective model of media education: utilising stories about network risks so the child will be prepared and informed so as to counter negativity. The lack of this protective model – will see an increase in the child's feeling of abandonment, which is criticized in most countries, while a family media immunity also performs this function. In terms of the Ukrainian reality, a defensive model is still required (Naidonova, 2012), because not all parents understand the importance of, or pay attention to how and which media is used by their children. According to this model, the library using its own information resources (thematic headings of websites, blogs, podcasts on the topic, online video channels, bibliographical aids, colorful flyers, comics, attractions, etc...) and other authoritative resources on the Internet can spread knowledge about various threats, and risks that can arise during interaction with media. In addition, maintaining a protective model of media education, youth libraries should provide information

¹ Media immunity of personality makes him/her able to withstand an aggressive media environment, provides psychological well-being while consumption of media products, providing media awareness, the ability to choose the right information, avoid information «garbage», to protect themselves from potentially harmful information on the basis of direct and hidden influences.

support to young parents on how to promote the required knowledge, skills and abilities for safe media use for children from an early age. Currently, such activities for young parents are rare, amongst other measures, however, these should be increased, because the family unit is where children first learn about the media. And from that, how the family communicates dictates what children learn from their parents (Zander, 2007).

Numerous art events that take place annually in each library for youth and teenagers, the activity of clubs, exhibitions of literature of different types of art through various media – everything is called upon to promote the aesthetic taste of young readers. In this way the library is attached to the aesthetic model of media education, which serves as media filter that protects from harmful influences.

Critical thinking is a nuclear mechanism of media literacy, the ability to build on their own reasoned and adequate attitude to media products (Naidonova, 2012). Traditional library lessons are focused on getting readers to work on skills with books, texts which are upgraded through the use of information and communication technologies – libraries' means of the creation of critical thinking. The critical model of media education aims at the development of critical thinking.

The creative model of media education is the most efficient and widely-used method globally. By creating their own media products, the child understands the mechanisms of media influence, begins to treat other media products more critically and is not suppressed, but rather carried away, and inspired with the learning process. In the context of the above mentioned we will give specific examples which were clarified in this study. Most libraries moderate virtual platforms to encourage young users to be included in the development of information resources focused on their peers, or offer consult support for creating of own media resources: blogs, podcasts, video channels etc... A striking example of how library attracts young people to create media resources, is 20 high-quality video channels «Provesin of Ternopil» about young Ternopil writers – the project was initiated by the Ternopil Regional Library for Youth, and implemented by the joint efforts of librarians, talented young journalists and writers.

At Poltava Regional Youth Library, which is named after Gonchar, a studio on media culture and media literacy «Open Space» is operating. Through the activities of this studio the youth of Poltava study and analyze different types of texts and media, critically analyze media messages, master techniques of psychological defenses against negative information, as well as safe behavior in cyberspace and they also acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to enable transition from media literacy to creating media art.

The activities of the Journalism club «smART start» encourage young people in creative writing and provided basic knowledge on foundational skills of journalism, to effectively analyze and transform information in the most readable form. This club was based at the Kharkiv Regional Library for Youth. In the future the library wants to increase this type of activity and to organize free university-style courses related to media literacy. This form of work involves lectures, workshops, seminars and public discussions. It is expected that the program of Free University courses will be planned in a way to promote high levels of media cultural awareness amongst a wide range of readers and utilizing a diverse range of modern media resources. Also, the program will take into account the needs of young professionals in the field of content management, copywriting, journalism and other media areas.

The platform for expression through creativity «I have something to say!» is moderated by State Library of Ukraine for Youth. Anyone who wishes, young readers and/or friends of the library, can organize and make a presentation of their creative works on the site and carry out information campaigns using the platform «I have

something to say!». The library helps to create an online presentation of creativity, with video podcasts, and cosplay (costume play) etc...

A poll conducted for the State Library of Ukraine for Youth in the Regional Library for Youth in 2014 showed that 62 % of libraries for youth and teenagers both independently, and with the support of educational institutions, promoted media awareness, and enhanced media literacy, and media competence in the youth environment. Among the popular mechanisms were the following:

- Workshops to create blogs, podcasts, support of own video channel;
- Training on safe use of electronic media, on an introduction to web design, short animation, scribing;
- Library lessons, workshops, skills-oriented on search of reliable information on the Internet and proper citation of electronic resources taking into account legal aspects of interaction with the media;
- Studios for discussion of books read and interesting Web resources, and similar groups in social networks;
- Watching of cinematically acclaimed movies in order to enhance aesthetic taste;
- Training, guidelines for media education, media literacy for library professionals.

The survey also identified factors that hinder the implementation of library initiatives aimed at building media literacy and media competence (look at the Figure 1). Respondents included such factors as: insufficient guidance materials (78,6 %), low media competence of librarians (50 %), lack of information and communication technology (50 %), lack of time to explore the possibility of inclusion of libraries in the process of media education (35,7 %), lack of established channels of cooperation with educational institutions (21,4 %).

Figure 1. What is missing for library to support initiatives aimed at building media competence?

CONSLUSION

The high level of information and network media culture is one of the main challenges that faces young people in an information and knowledge-based society. Libraries now have the necessary tools in order to help the reader in the preparation of effective and comfortable interaction in virtual information environments by

conducting appropriate measures independently, or by acting as intermediaries between the readers and experts who are ready to share this knowledge and experience.

One of the priorities, which require libraries to consolidate efforts, is a development of clear strategic actions in the network of youth libraries and the creation of networked information and media culture and to ensure this activity isn't chaotic, but purposeful and well organized. In addition, libraries will continue to:

- Raise the level of their own competencies;
- Create methods of creation of information network and media culture;
- Establish cooperation with other institutions engaged in similar activities;
- Educate users to work with information and acquire knowledge using clear and close communication channels (blogs, social networks, mobile applications, etc.);
- Carry out regular monitoring of library and information activities in order to summarize the experience and improvement of library methods and means of information and network creation and media competencies of youth and young adults.

This activity will not only assist libraries to consolidate their current place in the provision of Ukrainian information services, but also to facilitate their transformation in developing libraries of innovation – libraries of a knowledge-based society.

REFERENCES

- Bozhok, N.O. (2013). Psykholohichni osoblyvosti yunatskoho viku ta yikh vplyv na formuvannya frustratsiinoi tolerantnosti maibutnoho fakhivtsia [Psychological peculiarities of adolescence and their effect on formation of frustration tolerance of future specialist]. *Psykholohiia osobystosti*, 1 (4), 187–194 [in Ukrainian].
- Gorshenin Institute. (2013, April 19). *Sovremennaya molodezh Ukrainyi: svobodnoe vremya* [The Modern Youth of Ukraine: Free Time]. Retrieved from: http://test.gorshenin.ua/programs/researches/2380_sovremennaya_molodezh_ukraini.html [in Russian].
- Instytut sotsialnoi ta politychnoi psykholohii NAPN Ukrainy. (2010). *Kontseptsiiia vprovadzhennia media osvity v Ukraini* [The Concept of Introducing Media Education in Ukraine, Approved by the Resolution of the Presidium of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine dated 20 May 2010, the protocol № 1-7/6-150]. Retrieved from: <http://balakliya-school2.edu.kh.ua/Files/downloads/Концепція%20впровадження%20медіаосвіти%20в%20Україні.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
- Internet Asotsiatsiia Ukrainy. (2018). *Proniknovenie interneta v Ukraine* [Internet penetration in Ukraine]. Retrieved from: https://inau.ua/sites/default/files/file/1806/ui_factum_group_ii_kvartal_2018.pdf [in Russian].
- Krasii, M. (2014). Biblioteka ta chytach u virtualnomu prostori. Mistse zustrichi. Vseukrainske sotsiolohichne doslidzhennia [Library and Reader in Cyberspace: A place of meeting (Ukrainian National Sociological Research)]. *Bibliosvit*, 49, 56–68 [in Ukrainian].
- LB.ua. (2013, April 2). *Dlya chego ukrainskoy molodezhi nuzhen Internet? – issledovanie* [Why do Ukrainian youth need the Internet? – research]. Retrieved from: https://lb.ua/society/2013/04/02/194959_ukrainskoy_molodezhi_nuzhen.html [in Russian].
- Kinney, B. (2010). The Internet, Public Libraries, and the Digital Divide. In *Public Library Quarterly*, 29 (2), 104–161 [in English].
- McShane, I. (2011). Public libraries, digital literacy and participatory culture. In *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education* (Vol. 32 (3), pp. 383–397) [in English].
- Naidonova, L.A. (2012). Sotsialno-psykholohichna model mediaosvity: osoblyvosti realizatsii [Media Education in Ukraine, specificity of implementation of socio-psychological

- model]. In *Naukovi studii iz sotsialnoi ta politychnoi psykholohii* (Vol. 30, pp. 269–283) [in Ukrainian].
- Podoliak, L.G. (2013). *Psykholohiia rannoho yunatstva (Lektsiia z vikovoi psykholohii)* [Psychology of Early Youth (Lecture of Age Psychology)]. In *Herald of Psychology and Pedagogy*. Retrieved from: [http://www.psyh.kiev.ua/Психологія_раннього_юнацтва_\(Лекція_з_вікової_психології\)](http://www.psyh.kiev.ua/Психологія_раннього_юнацтва_(Лекція_з_вікової_психології)) [in Ukrainian].
- Poyntz, S.R., & Jenness, P. (2018). Youth and Media Culture. In *The Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education*. Retrieved from: <http://education.oxfordre.com/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264093-e-75> [in English].
- Tripp, L. (2011). Digital Youth, Libraries, and New Media Literacy. In *The Reference Librarian* (Vol. 52, pp. 329–341) [in English].
- Yakushko, T.O., & Yaroshenko, T.O. (2012). *Tekhnologii Veb 2.0 dlia bibliotek i korystuvachiv: novi mozhlyvosti rozvytku bibliotechnoho seredovyscha : posib. dlia treneriv za prohr. pidvyshch, kvalifikatsii* [Web 2.0 Technologies for Libraries and Users: new possibilities for library environments: a guide for trainers according to a training program]. Kyiv: Summit Book [in Ukrainian].
- Zander, E. (2007). Media v yunatskomu vitsi [Media in adolescence]. In *Nezaleznyj kul'turolohičnyj casopys «I»* (Vol. 46, pp. 212–222). Retrieved from: <http://www.ji.lviv.ua/engl-vers/archiv-eng.htm> [in Ukrainian].

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РОЗВИТОК МЕРЕЖЕВОЇ ТА МЕДІА КУЛЬТУРИ ЗАСОБАМИ БІБЛІОТЕКИ ДЛЯ ЮНАЦТВА

Це дослідження зосереджується на діяльності українських бібліотек для молоді, а також їхній ролі у розвитку інформаційної та мережевої медіа культури та обізнаності серед молоді. Завдяки моніторингу звітності молодіжних бібліотек та аналізу контенту веб-сайтів, блогів та сторінок соціальних мереж були виявлені існуючі бібліотечні засоби у створенні молодіжних інформаційних мереж та медіа-культури. Метод порівняльного аналізу дав змогу порівняти обрані бібліотечні засоби для створення молодіжних інформаційних мереж та медіа-культури з акцентом на індивідуальні психологічні характеристики молоді (у ранньому та пізньому юнацькому віці) та особливості моделі української медіа освіти. Розкрито існуючі методи та інструменти для створення інформаційних мереж та підвищення медіа компетентності молоді з урахуванням психологічних та вікових факторів. Також розглядається можливість додавання бібліотек до української моделі засобів масової інформації. Доведено, що одним із пріоритетів, які вимагають від бібліотек об'єднувати зусилля, є розробка чітких стратегічних дій у мережі молодіжних бібліотек та створення мережевої культури інформації та медіа, а також забезпечення того, щоб ця діяльність була не хаотичною, а цілеспрямованою та добре організованою.

Ключові слова: культура медіа, молодь, бібліотеки, інформаційна мережа, медіа-компетентність, медіа-освіта.